

Physical Education-Teacher Education in the United States: Preparing Tomorrow's Teachers for America's Classrooms

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to examine university programs that prepare physical education teachers in the United States of America. Information will focus on accredited versus non-accredited programs and the status of physical education and physical activity of school aged youth in America.

Key words: physical education, teacher education, accredited programs.

Introduction

Certification programs for physical education teachers are designed to empower

For the first time in American history, youth 20 years of age and younger, are not expected to outlive their parents. Between 1980 and 2004, the rate of obesity "tripled among children and adolescents, with 1 in 3 children overweight or obese" [3]. Of children 6-11 years old in the United States, 33% are categorized as overweight and 17 % are obese. Youth between the ages of 12 -19, 34% are listed as overweight, while 17.6% are obese [11]. Many variables come into play in relation to the health problems children and youth are having related to a lack of physical activity. America's youngest citizens are driven to and from school, consume fast food (e.g. McDonald's, Kentucky Fried Chicken), play video games, and lead sedentary lives. Studies indicate that "65% of all high school students did not meet the recommended levels of physical activity which include 60 minutes per day on five of the previous seven days. Additionally, "fewer than 1/3 of all children 6-17 years old engage in vigorous activity..." [11]. Finally, factors such as the reduction or elimination of physical education from the school curriculum must be considered as well.

As diverse as the United States is, so are the expectations for physical education in our

public schools. Many variables come into play to explain this. For example, 82% of states (n=42) require physical education teachers to be licensed at the elementary level. However, 57% of states (n= 29) allow an elementary classroom teacher to teach elementary physical education [11]. Permitting a classroom teacher, who does not possess any specialized preparation in physical education, to teach elementary physical education is very problematic. Another variable relating to this is the recommended amount of time students should be receiving in physical education each week in the United States. The National Association for Sport and Physical Education (NASPE) recommends 30 minutes per day (150 minutes per week) at the primary school level and 45 minutes per day (225 minutes per week) at the secondary level. However, to date, only one state, Alabama, meets these national recommendations at the kindergarten through 12th grade (K-12) level [11]. Finally, while the amount of time K-12 students spend in physical education has decreased, their sedentary time has increased. On an average school day 25% of high school students spend three or more hours using a computer (not related to school work) or playing video games. Thirty-five percent also spend three or more hours watching television on an average school day [11]. This being said, parents are beginning to realize the importance of physical education in American schools. In a

survey conducted by NASPE “95% of parents surveyed believed that daily physical activity helps with academics and should be part of the curriculum in K-12,” while seventy-six percent of parents thought that more physical education could control obesity [11]. The health related outcomes of the future generation of American citizens is at stake. In 2010, America spent approximately \$344 billion (€ 242.5 billion) on obesity related medical expenses [11]. Thus, it is even more important that physical education-teacher education (PETE) programs prepare future teachers with innovative and effective pedagogical practices.

The above statistics reveal the difficulties in not having a national curriculum for physical educators to implement. While The National Association for Sport and Physical Education has defined quality learning experiences through kindergarten through 12th grade physical education standards, the United States does not have a national curriculum. Thus, it is imperative that physical education-teacher education programs prepare teacher candidates who are qualified to implement these standards (Appendix A). The purpose of this manuscript is to examine the university programs that prepare future physical educators, focusing on accredited versus non accredited programs. Additionally, an analysis will be provided on how one accredited physical education- teacher education program prepares future physical education teachers.

University students in the United States have many options when selecting Physical Education-Teacher Education (PETE) as their area of study. Ayers and Housner noted there were approximately 200 PETE programs within the 50 states [2], including public and private universities. There are two main tracks for teacher education in the United States: non-accredited and accredited programs. Non-accredited programs are not required to undergo any type of external review process on a regularly scheduled basis, nor are they obligated to meet the standards established by their professional organizations. In the case of Physical Education-Teacher Education in the United States, that professional organization would be NASPE. An “accredited” university

teacher education program has “met national standards set by the teaching field at large and has undergone rigorous external and impartial review by professionals, policymakers and representatives of the public [4].” Additionally, an on-site evaluation is completed by three to eight examiners over a three day visit to the university. Accredited universities are certified as having demonstrated “best practices,” which are the most up-to-date instructional strategies as related to specific fields of study (e.g. PETE). Metzler [8] identified several best practices that have emerged in teacher education over the last several years including:

recruiting better students, providing a balance between content and pedagogy, assessing candidates from admission to graduation and through their first few years of teaching, providing early and longer field experiences, assessing university programs to demonstrate how well they meet standards.

Best pedagogical practices in physical education-teacher education have been developed by The National Association for Sport and Physical Education (NASPE). The 2008 edition of the National Standards and Guidelines for Physical Education-Teacher Education include six standards and 28 elements (See Appendix B for a complete listing). For a PETE program to be accredited, the faculty and students must meet all of the standards and elements established by NASPE. These standards, which outline the minimal competencies expected of a new physical education teacher, include [10]:

- Scientific and theoretical knowledge: Physical education teacher candidates know and apply discipline-specific scientific and theoretical concepts critical to the development of physically educated individuals.
- Skill based and fitness based competence: physical education teacher candidates are physically educated individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary to demonstrate competent movement performance and health enhancing fitness as delineated in the NASPE K-12 standards.
- Planning and implementation: Physical education teacher candidates plan and implement developmentally appropriate

learning experiences aligned with local, state, and national standards to address the diverse needs of all students.

- Instructional delivery and management: Physical education teacher candidates use effective communication and pedagogical skills and strategies to enhance student engagement and learning.
- Impact on student learning: Physical education teacher candidates use assessments and reflection to foster student learning and inform decisions about instruction.
- Professionalism: Physical education teacher candidates demonstrate dispositions that are essential to becoming effective professionals.

For accredited universities, this process is lengthy, rigorous, involves years of data collection on teacher candidates, an electronic report submission by faculty and on-site visits by the accrediting organization. The accreditation process has many stakeholders. These include the university teacher education program as a whole in addition to the individual teacher education content areas (science, mathematics, etc.). So, why would a university and PETE program seek accreditation? Multiple reasons exist, depending upon who is asked. From the University's perspective, reasons focus on an on-going reflective practice assessing the quality and improvement of the program, access to federal funding, and acknowledgment the program is teaching and implementing up-to-date pedagogical practices [13]. Additionally, the university's teacher education program receives the "seal of approval" from the accrediting body in having met the national standards [4].

The National Council for the Accreditation of Teacher Education (NCATE) states that a graduate of an accredited program benefits from such an experience in that "Many states have reciprocity agreements based on graduation from NCATE accredited schools, so graduates of NCATE accredited schools will generally find it easier to apply for licensure when they move out of state" [4]. For example, a graduate of Illinois State University's PETE program will only be licensed to teach physical education in the State of Illinois. If the graduate were to move to the

state of New York, they must meet the licensing requirements for the state of New York.

As of this writing, there are two accrediting institutions in the United States: The National Council for the Accreditation of Teacher Education (NCATE) and the Teacher Education Accreditation Council (TEAC). NCATE was established in 1954 and accredits approximately 640 institutions, while the Teacher Education Accreditation Council (TEAC) started in 1997, accredits approximately 90 universities. However, in October, 2010, both agencies merged to form one organization: The Council for the Accreditation of Educator Preparation (CAEP), representing a unified perspective on teacher education. The merger of these two organizations is expected to be complete by 2012.

While there are national standards and accrediting bodies, each university has the academic freedom to establish their own assessments for measuring each standard. Thus, there is a high level of individuality from each institution. Once students are accepted into a teacher preparation program, course assignments and assessments are associated with the accreditation process. At Illinois State University, PETE faculty incorporate the National Standards and Guidelines for Physical Education-Teacher Education into their course content (Appendix C). All accredited material is submitted through an electronic portfolio maintained by each teacher candidate. This information is used to generate program reports which include aggregated data submitted for accreditation purposes. As a specific example, KNR 158: Instructional Strategies in Physical Education is the first major class a teacher candidate completes at Illinois State University. Candidates are taught the mechanics of designing a lesson plan, participate in peer teaching, and complete analysis of teaching performance. Examples of assignments in this course include, but are not limited to, designing and implementing four lesson plans and self-analysis of DVD recordings of each teaching experience. The professor analyzes each DVD recording as well and a grade is assigned. The fourth lesson is submitted as evidence to the teacher candidates' electronic portfolio and their

final grade for this assignment is recorded for accreditation purposes by the professor. These particular assignments relate to the National Standards and Guidelines for Physical Education-Teacher Education # 3: Planning and Implementation and #4: Instructional Delivery and Management. It should be noted that professors are responsible for recording data on each physical education-teacher education major every semester. Data are analyzed in relation to each standard, reports completed and submitted. Through this reflective process, programmatic changes are made as determined by the analysis of the data.

The typical timeline for an accreditation process includes ongoing data collection, a seven year review cycle, and a report submitted one year prior to the on campus visit by board examiners. In addition to the faculty time and resources dedicated to the accreditation process, which is above and beyond typical faculty workloads, there is a financial cost to each university. The fees assessed a university seeking accreditation are determined on a sliding scale. For instance, a university graduating 1150 or more new teachers each year would pay an annual fee of \$4,695 (€3279) to NCATE. Over a course of seven years, a university would pay a total of \$32,865 (€22,953) prior to an on-site visit by the board of examiners. This does not include any additional fees for the on-site visit. The number of examiners visiting the university can range from three to eight, with an average cost of \$1750 (€1222) for each examiner visiting the campus. If eight examiners are assigned, the total cost to the university would be an additional \$14,000 (€9778) for the onsite visit. Requirements also include that the university pay for hotel accommodations, transportation, meals, supplies, computer rentals and workrooms at the hotel [5]. Decisions based on the review of the written report and the onsite visit by the board of examiners can lead to programs being accredited or having their accreditation revoked.

Physical Education-Teacher Education at Illinois State University

Teacher education has a long and rich history at Illinois State University. At its founding in 1857, it was stipulated that the school would

be the Illinois State Normal School. The primary purpose of a normal school was to train teachers for the state's common schools. Over time, normal schools evolved into teachers colleges and finally into multipurpose universities. Unlike many other schools, however, Illinois State University has maintained its normal school identity into the 1960's by retaining the word normal in its name [7]. The Physical Education-Teacher Education (PETE) program has been in existence for over 100 years and has established itself as one of the largest teacher education programs in the country, with over 250 undergraduate students currently enrolled in the program.

State Requirements

In the United States, education programs are overseen by the individual states rather than through the federal government. In the state of Illinois, education of children in grades Kindergarten through High School (12th Grade) and teacher education is governed by the Illinois State Board of Education (ISBE). The ISBE is the state agency that certifies licenses to teacher education graduates and sets standards for teacher education programs that must be met in order for candidates to receive their teaching licenses. These standards include technology competencies and the successful completion of three state level examinations. Technology competencies help to ensure that teacher candidates are proficient in a variety of technology exercises from spread sheets to desktop publishing. With regard to examinations, the first is the State of Illinois Basic Skills Test and is required to be taken relatively early in a teacher candidate's program of study. This test measures the mathematics, reading and writing skills of future teachers. A minimum grade must be achieved before the teacher candidate is allowed to proceed in the program of study. The Academic Content Area Exam is the second state level exam and is taken approximately midway through the program of study. Each program of study requires successful completion of its Academic Content Area exam. Thus, each teaching field, whether it is physical education-teacher education, history, art, English, foreign

languages, mathematics or any of the 29 teacher education programs on campus has a state level exam specifically designed to assess content knowledge in that field. During a teacher candidate's final semester at the university, the Assessment of Professional Teaching Exam is taken to measure the pedagogical skills of the teacher candidate relative to their program of study. A teacher candidate must pass the pedagogy exam in order to receive a teaching license in the state of Illinois.

College of Education Requirements

At Illinois State University, all teacher candidates, regardless of their field of study, are required to take coursework through the College of Education. The mission of the College of Education is "the preparation and continuing professional development of teachers" [1]. The series of five courses taken by all teacher candidates helps to ensure that content and class experiences are consistent for all programs. The content of these courses include child growth and development, issues in secondary education, literacy in the content area, instructional methods at the secondary level and philosophical foundations of education.

Additionally, in 1992 the College of Education began the implementation of a campus-wide Performance-Based Assessment (PBA) System. "The PBA system establishes critical points at which teacher candidates will be assessed" [1] and has identified various accreditation standards and requirements established by the Illinois State Board of Education. This collection of assessments and requirements were developed to ensure that all teacher candidates possess the knowledge, skills, and dispositions required for successful teaching careers. In addition, it ensures that Illinois State University teacher education programs meet the Illinois State Board of Education and national accreditation requirements [6]. These PBA standards are linked to course requirements in the College of Education as well as to course requirements in the Physical Education-Teacher Education program. Linking state certification and accreditation requirements with coursework helps to make these requirements relevant and

ensures that they are taught and assessed at appropriate points in the teacher candidate's program of study.

Lastly, the College of Education oversees the final field experience, student teaching. Student teaching is an intensive field experience where a teacher candidate spends a semester (16 weeks) in a school setting with varying responsibilities for the delivery and assessment of course content in their field of study. In PETE, teacher candidates are certified in grades K-12, resulting in two student teaching placements. Thus, during the 16 week semester, a teacher candidate will be placed for 8 weeks at an elementary site (grades K-5) and the other half of the semester (8 weeks), is spent at a secondary site (grades 6-12). Every effort is made to place teacher candidates at schools that will provide an optimal learning experience for all concerned, the teacher candidate and the pupils at the school.

Kinesiology and Recreation Requirements

The School of Kinesiology and Recreation at Illinois State University offers five major areas of study: Recreation Management, Therapeutic Recreation, Athletic Training, Exercise Science and Physical Education-Teacher Education. Students enrolled in Athletic Training, Exercise Science and Physical Education-Teacher Education complete a common core of Kinesiology classes. These courses include Human Anatomy and Physiology, Principles and Applications of Field-Based Assessment, Socio-Psychological Perspectives in Physical Activity, Motor Learning, Exercise Physiology, and Biomechanics. This common core reflects the faculty's belief in the importance of understanding the academic discipline of kinesiology as a whole and provides students with a broad understanding of the various sub-disciplines in the field. At some universities these classes are taught in a variety of departments such as biology or psychology. A strength of the program at Illinois State University is that these courses are taught by professors of kinesiology.

Physical Education-Teacher Education Requirements

PETE teacher candidates at Illinois State University undergo a rigorous course of study in the pedagogy of teaching physical education. Course content represents cutting edge research in the field of pedagogy and is taught by professors with active research agendas and physical education teaching experience in K-12 public schools. Just as with the College of Education requirements, Physical Education-Teacher Education courses are designed to provide teacher candidates with the skills, knowledge and dispositions to become effective teachers of physical education.

Towards that end, the faculty have designed courses that emphasize two broad areas: pedagogical content knowledge and pedagogical knowledge. Pedagogical content knowledge focuses on the ability to teach a variety of skills and activities to K-12 students. To accomplish that, teacher candidates enroll in four courses: Teaching Team Sports, Teaching Individual/Dual Sports and Activities, Teaching Dance and Tumbling/Gymnastics Forms and Promoting Physical Activity and Fitness in Physical Education. It is important to note that while skill acquisition is certainly a desirable outcome of these courses; the emphasis is on attaining the necessary pedagogical skills to teach activities. Teacher candidates learn effective skill progressions, cues, equipment needs, and strategies to use in their future teaching.

Pedagogical knowledge is attained through a series of three methods courses, where teaching skills are taught and implemented. An initial course, Instructional Strategies in Physical Education, focuses on effective teaching practices that are unique to the field of physical education. Content development, management skills, use of feedback, writing of objectives and lesson planning are stressed. This information is applied by the teacher candidates in a series of four peer teaching experiences throughout the semester. Each teaching experience is digitally filmed and the teacher candidate completes an extensive self-evaluation prior to a final evaluation by the professor. The second

methods course is Teaching Elementary Physical Education where the content of the initial class is built upon with an emphasis on elementary (K-5) physical education. Developmentally appropriate activities and curriculum for children are stressed. As in the initial methods class, the information is applied in an elementary field experience where teacher candidates are placed in an elementary school to observe and assist an elementary physical education teacher as well as instruct children at the school. The final methods class is Secondary Methods and Practices in Physical Education. Again, the foundational knowledge acquired in the Instructional Strategies course is built upon but in this course, the emphasis is on effective teaching practices at the secondary (grade 6-12) level. Adolescent development, secondary curricular practices and developmentally appropriate curriculum at the secondary level is stressed. This course also has an intensive field experience where teacher candidates are placed at the middle school level (grades 6-8) and teach a series of classes to pupils. As in the previous class, each teaching episode is digitally recorded for evaluation by the teacher candidates as well as the class professor.

The emphasis on analysis of one's own teaching through digital recording is a unique strength of the program. It should be noted that the evaluation rubrics used to assess both lesson plans and teaching experiences are standardized. Teacher candidates begin to use these rubrics in the initial methods class and continue to use them through the elementary and secondary methods classes as well as in their student teaching. Familiarity with faculty expectations and a consistent programmatic message help develop a teacher candidate who truly represents the philosophy and goals of the PETE program. Learning to continuously self-evaluate and interpret data collected during self-evaluations help teacher candidates learn what it means to be a reflective teacher and chart their own development as a teacher. Additionally, the data derived from the teaching evaluations is an invaluable source of continual program assessment for the PETE program.

Prior to a teacher candidate's 16 week student teaching experience, during the last semester of studies, all PETE majors will have completed a minimum of 100 clinical hours in Pre-school through 12th grade settings. These settings range from observing and assisting in the gymnasium to teaching physical education lessons. In addition to the courses previously mentioned in this paper, there are two specific requirements that are unique to the PETE program at Illinois State University. The first is completed early in the program of studies (second semester) in Motor Development. During this course, teacher candidates are required to plan and implement physical activities for pre-school aged children (3-5 years of age). Activities are based on developmentally appropriate motor skill progressions and theories of human motor development. The second experience occurs in the candidates' last year on campus, in Adapted Physical Education. The Adapted Physical Education course focuses on teaching physical education to students with disabilities. Federal education laws in the United States require that all students with disabilities must receive physical education based on their unique need. Thus, every physical education candidate should be prepared to work with students with disabilities in the public school setting. A distinctive feature of this course is that each candidate completes a 14 week clinical experience in a public school setting working with students with disabilities. For a complete list of course requirements at ISU, please see the program of study in Appendix D.

On a final note, the current economic climate of the United States makes for a challenging job market with public schools having to lay off teachers to save money. Even with this economic downturn, Illinois State University PETE graduates are still enjoying a high placement rate when seeking jobs. For a teacher preparation program, this means it is even more imperative to graduate teachers who are as competent and prepared as they possible can be. A well prepared teacher who is teaching a quality physical education program will stand a better chance of keeping his or her faculty position.

The purpose of this manuscript was to examine university programs that prepare future physical education teachers, specifically focusing on accredited programs. It is hoped that an examination of one high quality teacher preparation program in physical education can open a dialog with other pedagogy specialists. In the United States, there is one major accrediting agency that identifies competencies for teacher candidates. Since individual programs are allowed to determine their own methods of assessment, there is a tremendous variety of university requirements, state examinations and program requirements. While every program in the United States and in Europe have their own unique characteristics, an exchange of ideas and best pedagogical practices can help inform all who are responsible for preparing physical education teachers.

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Appendix A

Moving into the Future: National Standards for Physical Education (for students in K-12 physical education) (NASPE, 2004, p. 1)

Standard 1: Demonstrates competency in motor skills and movement patterns need to perform a variety of physical activities.

Standard 2: Demonstrates an understanding of movement concepts, principles, strategies, and tactics as they apply to the learning and performance of physical activities.

Standard 3: Participates regularly in physical activity.

Standard 4: Achieves and maintains a health-enhancing level of physical fitness.

Standard 5: Exhibits responsible personal and social behavior that respects self and others in physical activity settings.

Standard 6: Values physical activity for health, enjoyment, challenge, self-expression, and/or social interaction.

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Appendix B

National Standards and Guidelines for Physical Education-Teacher Education (2008)

Standard 1: Scientific and Theoretical Knowledge

Physical education teacher candidates know and apply discipline specific scientific and theoretical concepts critical to the development of physically educated individuals.

Elements - Teacher candidates will:

- 1.1 Describe and apply physiological and biomechanical concepts related to skillful movement, physical activity and fitness.
- 1.2 Describe and apply motor learning and psychological/behavioral theory related to skillful movement, physical activity and fitness.
- 1.3 Describe and apply motor development theory and principles related to skillful movement, physical activity and fitness.
- 1.4 Identify historical, philosophical and social perspectives of physical education issues and legislation.
- 1.5 Analyze and correct critical elements of motor skills and performance concepts.

Standard 2: Skill-based and Fitness-Based Competence

Physical education teacher candidates are physically educated individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary to demonstrate competent movement performance and health-enhancing fitness as delineated in the NASPE K-12 Standards.

Elements - Teacher candidates will:

- 2.1 Demonstrate personal competence in motor skill performance for a variety of physical activities and movement patterns.
- 2.2 Achieve and maintain a health-enhancing level of fitness throughout the program.
- 2.3 Demonstrate performance concepts related to skillful movement in a variety of physical activities.

Standard 3: Planning and Implementation

Physical education teacher candidates plan and implement developmentally appropriate learning experiences aligned with local, state and national standards to address the diverse needs of all students.

Elements - Teacher candidates will:

- 3.1 Design and implement short- and long-term plans that are linked to program and instruction goals, as well as a variety of student needs.
- 3.2 Develop and implement appropriate (e.g. measurable, developmentally appropriate, performance based) goals and objectives aligned with local, state, and/or national standards.
- 3.3 Design and implement content that is aligned with lesson objectives.
- 3.4 Plan for and manage resources to provide active, fair and equitable learning experiences.
- 3.5 Plan and adapt instruction for diverse student needs, adding specific accommodations and/or modifications for student exceptionalities.
- 3.6 Plan and implement progressive and sequential instruction that addresses the diverse needs of all students.
- 3.7 Demonstrate knowledge of current technology by planning and implementing learning experiences that require students to appropriately use technology to meet lesson objectives.

Standard 4: Instructional Delivery and Management

Physical education teacher candidates use effective communication and pedagogical skills and strategies to enhance student engagement and learning.

Elements - Teacher candidates will:

- 4.1 Demonstrate effective verbal and non-verbal communication skills across a variety of instructional formats.
- 4.2 Implement effective demonstrations, explanations and instructional cues and prompts to link physical activity concepts to appropriate learning experiences.
- 4.3 Provide effective instructional feedback for skill acquisition, student learning and motivation.
- 4.4 Recognize the changing dynamics of the environment and adjust instructional tasks based on student responses.
- 4.5 Use managerial rules, routines and transitions to create and maintain a safe and effective learning environment.
- 4.6 Implement strategies to help students demonstrate responsible personal and social behaviors in a productive learning environment.

Standard 5: Impact on Student Learning

Physical education teacher candidates use assessment and reflection to foster student learning and inform decisions about instruction.

Elements - Teacher candidates will:

- 5.1 Select or create appropriate assessments that will measure student achievement of goals and objectives.
- 5.2 Use appropriate assessments to evaluate student learning before, during and after instruction.
- 5.3 Use the reflective cycle to implement change in teacher performance, student learning and/or instruction goals and decisions.

Standard 6: Professionalism

Physical education teacher candidates demonstrate dispositions that are essential to becoming effective professionals.

Elements - Teacher candidates will:

- 6.1 Demonstrate behaviors that are consistent with the belief that all students can become physically educated individuals.
- 6.2 Participate in activities that enhance collaboration and lead to professional growth and development.
- 6.3 Demonstrate behaviors that are consistent with the professional ethics of highly qualified teachers.
- 6.4 Communicate in ways that convey respect and sensitivity.

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Appendix C

Physical Education Teacher Education Course Assignments included in the Accreditation Evaluation

KNR 156: Introduction to Physical Education-Teacher Education

- Physical fitness testing of majors

KNR 158: Instructional Strategies in Physical Education

- Lesson plan evaluation and teaching evaluation (by professor)
- Self -evaluation of teaching experience
- Reflection of teaching experiences

KNR 225: Motor Development

- Designing and implementing preschool level motor activities in a day care setting
- Lesson plan evaluation (by professor)
- Assessment of teacher candidates' fundamental motor skills (Test of Gross Motor Development-2)

KNR 221: Teaching Elementary Physical Education

- Designing and implementing elementary level motor activities in a public school setting
- Lesson plan evaluation and teaching evaluation (by professor)
- Self -evaluation of teaching experience
- Reflection of teaching experience

KNR 242: Secondary Methods and Practices in Physical Education

- Designing and implementing elementary level motor activities in a public school setting
- Lesson plan evaluation and teaching evaluation (by professor)

- Self -evaluation of teaching experience
- Reflection of teaching experiences

KNR 247: Promoting Physical Activity and Fitness in Physical Education

- Lesson plan evaluation and teaching evaluation
- Fitness assessment administered by KNR 247 students to KNR 156 majors
- Fitness self- assessment

STT 399: Student Teaching – Eight weeks at an elementary school and eight weeks at a secondary school

- Designing and implementing elementary level motor activities in a public school setting (8 weeks)
- Designing and implementing secondary level motor activities in a public school setting (8 weeks)
- Lesson plan evaluation and teaching evaluation (by professor)
- Lesson plan evaluation and teaching evaluation by public school teacher
- Self-Evaluation of teaching experience
- Reflection of teaching experiences

Appendix D

Physical Education-Teacher Education Plan of Study

Kinesiology core requirements:

COURSE	COURSE TITLE	CREDIT HOURS
KNR 181	Human Anatomy & Physiology	3
KNR 182	Human Anatomy & Physiology	3
KNR 240	Principles & Applications of Fitness Training	2
KNR 254	Socio-Psychological Perspectives Physical Activity	3
KNR 257	Motor Learning & Performance	3
KNR 280	Exercise Physiology	3
KNR 282	Biomechanics of Human Movement	3

Physical Education-Teacher Education Major Courses

KNR 156	Introduction to Physical Education-Teacher Education	2
KNR 158	Instructional Strategies in Physical Education	3
KNR 221	Teaching Elementary Physical Education	3
KNR 225	Motor Development	3
KNR 242	Secondary Methods & Practices in Physical Education	3
KNR 244	Teaching Team Sports	3
KNR 245	Teaching Individual/Dual Sport and Activities	3
KNR 246	Teaching Dance, Tumbling/Gymnastic Forms	2
KNR 247	Promoting Physical Activity & Fitness in Physical Education	3
KNR 341	Assessment in Physical Education	3
KNR 364	Senior Seminar in Physical Education	3
KNR 383	Adapted Physical Education	3

Professional Education Courses within the College of Education

PSY 215/C&I 210	Educational Psychology or Child Growth and Development	3
C&I 212	Issues in Secondary Education	2
C&I 214/216/216.08 or C&I 289.75/216.08	Reading in the Content Areas of Secondary Ed and Instructional/Eval Methods in Secondary Education or Secondary Ed. Lab for PE and Instructional Assessment and Literary Practices for Secondary Ed	6
EAF 228/231/235	Social or Historical Foundations or Intro to Philosophy of Education	3
	K-12 Student Teaching:	
STT 399.74	Secondary Student Teaching Section	6
STT 399.75	Elementary Student Teaching Section	6
	Recommended Electives:	
C&I 233.01	Middle Level Education & The Young Adolescent	3
PSY 302	Adolescent Development	3

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